

Certificate

MANUEL ANTONIO FERNANDEZ-VILLACAÑAS MARIN

participated in The 2019 Multidisciplinary International Conference of Research Applied to Defense and Security (MICRADS'19), scientific conference held between the 8th and 10th of May 2019, in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Organization

Honorary Chair

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read "Alvaro Karam", is written over a light blue horizontal line.

**MINISTÉRIO DA DEFESA
EXÉRCITO BRASILEIRO
DEPARTAMENTO DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA
INSTITUTO MILITAR DE ENGENHARIA
(Real Academia de Artilharia, Fortificação e Desenho/1792)**

To the General Chief of the Directorate of Economic Affairs SAF

Dear Sr

As local chair of MICRADS'19 – Multidisciplinary International Conference of Research Applied to Defense and Ssecurity, I am pleased to inform that the work “The transformation of the Defense and Security Sector to the New Logistics 4.0: Public-Private Cooperation as a necessary catalyst strategy”, submitted by Coronel (SAF) Dr. Manuel A. Fernández- Villacañas Marín, was accepted for publication and selected for oral presentation.

We are honored to invite Coronel Dr. Fernández-Villacañas to attend the conference, which will be held at the Instituto Militar de Engenharia (IME), at Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, from 8 to 10 of May, 2019.

In any case, we are at your disposal for any further information needed.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Robson Pacheco Pereira', written over a horizontal line.

Professor Robson Pacheco Pereira

MICRADS'19 Local Chair

IME/RJ

Rio de Janeiro, Brasil

Certificate

MANUEL ANTONIO FERNANDEZ-VILLACAÑAS MARIN

presented the article

"The transformation of the Defense and Security Sector to the New Logistics 4.0: Public-Private Cooperation as a necessary catalyst strategy"

in The 2019 Multidisciplinary International Conference of Research Applied to Defense and Security

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The transformation of the Defense and Security Sector to the New Logistics 4.0: Public-Private Cooperation as a necessary catalyst strategy

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Abstract: The logistical needs to develop and maintain both military and police weapon systems and support material, are being met to respond to a set of certain risks, which now imply the invasion of the territory as well as other threats, such as international terrorism, cyber-attacks, corruption, drug and arms trafficking, global organized crime, or the trafficking of human beings. The strategic support that will guide the new operative concepts and together with the acquisition of new military and police capabilities, is based nowadays, and will be increasingly in the future, on technology and logistics capacity. In this sense, the concepts of the new logistics have experienced a great catalyze with the digital transformation, which requires a complete organizational, cultural and strategic reinvention of both the armed and police forces and the defense and security industry. The qualitative research conducted has detected a gap in the reactive adaptation of the armed and police forces to the new logistics 4.0, in relation to its proactive implementation by the main companies of this sector. The implementation of public-private cooperation models, which in addition to involving advantages in the improvement of military and police efficiency as well as business development for the industrial sector, will involve the permanent and bidirectional transfer of knowledge among the structures implicated, including the adaptation and permanent dynamic adjustment to the great changes that the exponential digital evolution will imply.

Keywords: Digital transformation, logistics 4.0, defense and security industry 4.0, military logistics, armed and police forces, public-private cooperation.

1 Introduction

The vast changes that have taken place in this decade have made it necessary and evident for the armed and police forces of the international community, to understand the nature and current factors of the global environment that condition their internal activity. The risks and threats in our days and, therefore, the problems of defense and security, are much broader than those of other times as a result of their global impact,

the characteristics and possibilities of the new digital technologies applied, as well as of the "intelligent" armament used (Fernández-Villacañas, 2009).

Accordingly, the current logistic needs regarding the development and maintenance of weapons systems and their military and police support material are being covered by realistic and adjusted public budgets to give sufficient response to a set of certain risks, that within the framework of the New World Order, moderately implies the usual threat of invasion of the territory, and a significant presence of a new and diverse set of threats, such as international terrorism, cyber attacks, corruption, drug trafficking and trafficking of international arms, global organized crime, or the trafficking of human beings, which are supported by anonymous groups willing to achieve their objectives at the expense of insecurity and international social destabilization (Fernández-Villacañas, 2017).

The strategic support that will guide the development of new operational concepts and the acquisition of new military and police capabilities is based on three key premises. Firstly, that the present and future strategic environment is uncertain, complex and conflictive; secondly, that no crisis can be resolved satisfactorily with isolated military and police employment, which must be combined and integrated with other initiatives of a civil, political, economic, humanitarian or informational nature; and finally, that the military and police forces must have a balanced and an adequate catalog of capabilities both for the conventional conflicts and for irregular and hybrid combat, whose source of "military and police advantage" will be technology and logistics capabilities (García Arnáiz, 2017).

All of this has involved, since the end of the previous decade and the beginnings of the present one, a transformation of the defense and security sector, which has been largely driven by the development and implementation of the so-called new logistics in its adaptation to the global world. However, the new technological scenario represented by digital transformation, and in its scope, the implementation of the concepts of Industry 4.0 and Logistics 4.0 in this sector (Romero Garat, 2018), both in its public and private sphere, requires a complete organizational, cultural and strategic reinvention both the armed and police forces and the international industrial sector of defense and security, thus providing the international community and each of the countries with a dynamic redesign capability that can respond to the needs arising from the processes of exponential technological evolution, that this new paradigm carries with it.

2 Background and literature review

2.1 The New Logistics: Creating competitiveness and global sustainable development

In recent years, logistics has been acquiring a growing importance in the strategy of companies, and has become an essential factor for improving their competitiveness in a constantly changing global market. Thus, the application of improvements in the performance of methodologies and technologies in the logistics field, which have developed exponentially with the Internet, implicitly leads to obtaining competitive

advantages. These advantages are based not only on increasing efficiency and effectiveness in logistics management, but also on increasing the value provided to customers and global sustainability.

The new logistics is based on a conceptual transition from a "push" approach to a "pull" approach, developing new logistic models that are more efficient, sustainable, intelligent, agile, adaptable, scalable and resilient. The following figure summarizes the main aspects of traditional logistics and its evolution to the new logistics (Fernández-Villacañas, 2018).

THE TRADITIONAL LOGISTICS	THE NEW LOGISTICS
Competition for price	Competition for service
Transportation of large lots, rare	Transport of smaller and more frequent lots
Supply type push, driven by the offer	Supply type pull, driven by demand
Existence of large inventories	Inventory zero (just in time)
Focus on business by contracts	Focus on the integration of processes, with the use of ICTs for coordination and control
Distribution networks organized at multiple levels with reduced areas of influence	Global networks of logistics platforms and integrated distribution centers
Producers and marketers with their own organization, including transportation	Outsourcing to logistics operators (3PL and above), focus of the entrepreneur on activities of greater added value
Provision and sales focused on the country itself	Globalization of suppliers and customers
Low environmental awareness	Greater environmental awareness, circular economy and reverse logistics

Fig. 1. The Traditional Logistics Vs the New Logistics

On the other hand, the sustainability of global logistics (Fernández-Villacañas, 2008) and of Supply Chain Management, represents a strategy of transparent integration of the social, environmental and economic objectives of the organization, within the system of coordination of the main inter-organizational business processes, in order to improve the long-term economic results of each company and its supply chains (Carter & Rogers, 2008).

The development prospective of the new logistics with a long-term projection, has shaped the theory of Physical Internet (Montreuil, 2011), a vision that has been adopted both in the United States and in the European Union as the conceptual goal of logistics for 2050. It involves achieving an open global logistic system, based on a physical, digital and operational interconnectivity, through encapsulation, interfaces and protocol design, in order to move, store, perform, provide and use physical objects throughout the world in an economically, environmentally and in a socially efficient and sustainable way. The aim is to eliminate inefficiencies in global transport and waste management of logistics networks, in a similar way to what the Internet raised worldwide for information flows (Montreuil & Meller & Ballot, 2010).

Fig. 2. La perspectiva de evolución hacia el Physical Internet en 2050

Source: http://www.etp-logistics.eu/wpcontent/uploads/etpalice/Road_map_Alice_PIE.jpg , 17.12.2018

It will be necessary to create an open market for the transport of goods, with shared, open and adaptable distribution chains, in which the products will be transported in modular, standardized and intelligent containers, allowing each unit to be followed and controlled.

For this, it will be necessary to achieve a full level of global collaboration, redefining the competitive space, taking it out of the logistics processes, and taking it only to the points of sale in which customers define the market share of each product.

The viability of the Physical Internet will obviously require the implementation of existing digital enabling technologies, such as the Internet of Things, Cyberphysical Systems, Collaborative Robotics, eCommerce, BlockChain, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Additive Manufacturing and 3D Printing, Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Data Analytics, Predictive Maintenance, Simulation, Collaborative Economics, Cloud Computing, Cybersecurity, Machine Learning, etc., but above all, the incorporation of other more advanced and complex innovations resulting from the exponential technological evolution that are being developed now and in the future.

2.2 Logistics 4.0: The transformation of the New Logistics to the digital domain

Digital transformation can conceptually be defined as the process of organizational, cultural and strategic reinvention, both of companies and of public entities, necessary for the integral application of the technology that we call digital, which generates, processes, stores and uses data, information and intelligence, to improve its performance as well as its ability to quickly adapt to disruptive or radical changes generated in the environment. This technological scenario, an authentic new paradigm, is inducing the emergence of shorter and shorter management cycles, in which the environment changes continuously and increasingly faster, with a pace that we assume will continue to accelerate in the future, with an approach in exponential technological evolution as has already been highlighted.

The main catalyst for change and the cause of this continuous acceleration is the digital revolution, motivated by the expansion of the Internet, information and communication technologies, as well as the universalization of its use, which is in turn involving the transformation of our life style. In this way, we are today fully imbricated in a process of deployment of disruptive technologies that are profoundly modifying the business reality and the society in general. Although computer science signified a cyclopean advance in the mechanization and automation of the processes, and the later connection of the equipment between them, it also generated the beginning of a formidable process and distribution capacity of the information, the digital factor has exponentially multiplied the connectivity of all public and private actors, among which, logically, citizens are included as protagonists.

The inclusion of digital technologies and the transformation induced by them defines what has come to be called the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Effectively globalization, the universalization of the use of the Internet, the full automation of processes and the digitization of information, have led to an authentic Industrial Revolution, in which the hybridization of the physical and virtual world is taking place; products, machines, tools, factories, warehouses and vehicles are interconnecting each other and work automatically, an interconnection of all the elements of the value chain that is becoming intelligent and that is leading to the creation of authentic centered networks in the clients. In this way, the environment appears to be changing, hybrid, competitive, global, connected and interdependent.

The result of all this will allow us to achieve immediate answers in decision-making based on the information captured in real time, through intelligent systems and processes, without variability or errors, with full traceability in the process chains and total sustainability. All of this leads us to a new situation that will affect the way of producing and controlling processes, applying logistic models, and developing marketing and commercialization strategies.

In this way and totally linked to the concept of Industry 4.0, the concept of Logistics 4.0, which develops and assumes the concepts of the new logistics, transcends and emerges due to its importance. That is that logistics, as a key element of the industrial sector, cannot be kept aside. The Smart Factory implicitly assumes that manufacturing plants, facing a traditional centralization derived from the search for econo-

mies of scale by volume, now consider an intelligent relocation by factors of specialization and synergies, giving rise to the creation of different and immense networks distant from interconnected production units, which will imply that the raw materials, components and semi-finished products require greater mobility, be perfectly synchronized and guaranteed, participating in global supply networks and intra-industry trade. On the other hand, the life cycles of products in international markets tend to be continuously reduced and variations in their demands are increasingly difficult to estimate, so it is crucial to have greater connectivity and integration between the final and initial links of the global supply chains, as well as a greater capacity for the aggregation of data and automatic estimation, rigorous and real-time estimation of the different demands, with expert systems and artificial intelligence that assist the decision-making processes (Fernández-Villacañas, 2018). For all this, the New Logistics 4.0 will involve the optimization and full connection of all elements and processes of the supply chain, which should generate improvements in the efficiency and effectiveness of the management of orders and shipments, a production oriented to the individual customer which increasingly demands more personalized offers, the geolocation of customers, the simultaneous multimodal omnichannel, and the optimization of global routes, a full capacity for adaptation, the total international traceability of merchandise, the reduction of stock and space necessary for storage, automation of payments, etc. Smart logistics will not only better meet new demands, but will also more accurately locate and thoroughly know current and potential customers through the processing and interpretation of the data collected and the optimization of processes. Integration, holistic vision, coherence, innovation and flexibility are the key concepts to support the development of the New Logistics 4.0.

Finally, it is considered necessary to emphasize that the digital transformation and the emergence of Industry 4.0 and Logistics 4.0, beyond the technological developments and their deployment, and the reinvention of strategy, organization and corporate culture, requires, on the one hand, the development of a new holistic style of a humanitarian leadership, but also, on the other, the availability of a permanent digital leadership capacity that achieves the most critical element for the success of the analyzed evolution to be collaborate and be fully involved: this is the human factor.

3 The problem: The imbalances and delays between the adaptation to the new logistics 4.0 of the armed and police forces, and the companies in the defense and security industry

In order to know the state of involvement and development regarding the digital transformation in the companies of the defense and security industry in Spain, a qualitative research has been carried out to the main ones that accounted for approximately 85% of sales in 2016 of this sector (according to the Industrial of Defence Report of the Spanish MoD), all of them with European implantation and global projection (Airbus Defense and Space, Airbus Military, Indra Systems, Navantia, ITP Turboprop Industry, Expal Systems, Airbus Helicopters Spain, Cepsa, Iveco Spain, Santa Bárbara Sistemas, Naval Constructions P. Freire, Spanish Company of Aeronautical Systems,

ARPA, ...). The studie has been complemented with the vision of the two Associations that bring together most of the companies of the sector in Spain: the Spanish Association of Technology Companies of Defense, Aeronautics and Space (TEDAE), and the Association of Companies that contracting with the Public Sector and especially with the Armed and Security Forces (AESMIDE).

The results show that almost all companies consider that digital disruption implies opportunities for improvement in the efficiency, quality and flexibility of processes, which will produce the potential increase in operating profits. The defense and security industry is facing a new global context that poses major strategic and structural challenges, against which practically all have proactively raised lines of action.

However, the analysis as to the levels of initiative and implementation of these lines of action, in regard to the armed forces and police forces which are customers of these companies, both nationally and internationally, denote a reactive attitude. They are aware of the implications that the digital transformation will have on their operation levels and sustainability of their systems, but this has not translated into decided and effective action plans, possibly due to the lack of funding to address them.

In short, the probable existence of a gap in the reactive adaptation in the armed and police forces to the new logistics 4.0 is detected in relation to its proactive implementation by the main companies of the defense and security industry, with a delay and desynchronization that predictably will tend to grow due to the exponential technological evolution.

4 The solution: Public-Private Cooperation models as a necessary catalyst strategy. From operational outsourcing to cooperation

Outsourcing, as a strategic process of the transfer of public activities of the armed and police forces to the private sector, has been an aspect in the defense and security sector in continuous development since the beginning of the 90s in almost all the countries. Since then, their governments have opted for the implementation of outsourcing solutions in response to the growing demand for the in-service support of their weapons systems and progressive scarcity of resources, exploring better solutions in both technical and economic terms. Factors such as the acceleration of the technological evolution of armament and support material, which has made it increasingly difficult for the armed forces and police to maintain the necessary autonomy to ensure proper maintenance of their systems, or the increase in the cost of these equipment and the relative shortage of resources, especially qualified human resources, led to raise in the international arena to operational outsourcing as an effective solution to the new situation generated (Más Sabaté, 2000).

The management technique of outsourcing arises in the post-industrial era when competition in global markets begins (Girón, 1998). Through the externalization of those activities that are not critical, the entity specializes in its core activity, improving its competitiveness and the ability to adapt to rapid changes in the environment. But more than generic outsourcing (outsourcing), as a transfer of certain activities,

managed in a localized manner in the short term and with specific objectives, the concept of cooperation appears as a public-private co-management (co-sourcing). It is a strategy of global restructuring to obtain results that allows the best efforts of the organization to be oriented towards its nuclear activities and, with it, towards the fulfillment of its mission and objectives. The cooperative vision is to consider the provider of services as a partner with which a "win to win" relationship is established. To the extent that the organization internalizes that its fate is associated with that of its service provider and vice versa, the need to seek relationships in which there is mutual benefit becomes clearer (Fernández-Villacañas, 2007). Outsourcing, which in principle was proposed as a managerial technique, has potentially moved towards cooperation, partnerships and strategic alliances. It is not normally a question of formal companies, because the capital and patrimonies are independent and the symbiosis is such that it is not necessary to have a mercantile corporate relationship to be considered business partners.

In recent years, in the public sector, the public-private cooperation has become an international reference model that allows effective, efficient and synergistic integration of entrepreneurship with the management capacity of public services of the Administration. Through its mediation, certain collaboration formulas are established through which the public sector interacts with the private sector in the search for greater involvement of the latter in the development of certain complex projects, setting out a scheme of joint objectives, as well as sharing risks, costs and Benefits. It is a new conception of public management through which social needs are met in a different way, through a new frontier of relationship between the public sector and the private sector. The trend towards its use has been generalized in recent years as a management model for large projects, particularly in the innovation and high technology sectors, in internationalization initiatives and, in general, in all those in which it is necessary to guarantee high levels of competitiveness in advance. It is conceptualized as an economic-organizational model of dynamic and plural relationship, which groups a wide range of figures that maintain a link in time between two or more public and private organizations. It signifies a new conception by means of which a transition of a relationship between administration and industry of competitive character which is generated to another one of collaborative character.

On the other hand, the application of public-private cooperation in the defense and security sector entails a change of philosophy and mentality in the bodies involved in the public administration that will go on to manage certain essential services through a strategic partnership with private companies, assuming these shared risks and responsibilities with the armed forces and police forces. The advantages for both parties of the application of these models of public-private cooperation are clear. It can mean higher levels of rationalization and efficiency for the armed forces and police forces, as well as important savings via, among other factors, the reduction of military and police personnel and the technical assistance involved, as well as the reduction of costs of investment in facilities and equipment (avoiding duplicated expenses, heavy investments in spare parts stocks that must be maintained during long life cycles of the systems, reducing the costs of continuous training, technical documentation and its corresponding update, etc.). On the other, the defense and security industry can

obtain a new field of business development induced by the greater investment capacity derived from public savings, addressing the development of new defense and security systems that will make the strengthening of the industrial base and technology of that sector feasible.

Moreover, and perhaps most significantly, the functioning of the public-private co-management models imply the permanent and bidirectional transfer of knowledge between the public and private sectors, as well as the adaptation and the dynamic and permanent adjustment to major changes, that the exponential digital evolution will imply that "unique entity" formed by the agencies involved in the armed and police forces with the companies participating in the defense and security industry, in a contemporary way.

As a development of these models, the Spanish Air Force carried out the FENIX Project at the end of the previous decade. It was a series of applied research studies to improve the operational efficiency and profitability of surplus capacities of its Aerospace Maintenance Centers MRO (*Maestranzas Aéreas*) through the implementation of public-private cooperation models with the aerospace industry. The aim was to achieve improvements in the level of generation of air support services, with the lowest possible cost and risk. Previously, an international benchmarking study of the solutions applied by the Air Forces of the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Germany and Italy was carried out (Fernández-Villacañas, 2009 and 2011).

5 Conclusions

The work carried out in this paper has first of all analyzed the logistical needs of development and maintenance regarding weapon systems and support material for both the military and police. Nowadays they are based on technology and logistics capacity. In this sense, the new logistics have experienced a great catalyze with the digital transformation, which requires a complete organizational, cultural and strategic reinvention of both the armed and police forces and the defense and security industry. Secondly, the qualitative research conducted has detected a gap in the reactive adaptation of the armed and police forces to the new logistics 4.0, in relation to its proactive implementation by the main companies of this sector. In order to reduce this gap, the implementation of public-private cooperation models, in addition to involving advantages in the improvement of military and police efficiency, and business development for the industrial sector, will involve the permanent and bidirectional transfer of knowledge among the structures involved, as well as the adaptation and permanent dynamic adjustment to the vast changes that the exponential digital evolution will imply.

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